

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Optimal quadrature formulas for calculating Fourier coefficients in $W_2^{(m,0)}(0, 1)$ space

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Statement of the problem

We consider the following quadrature formula

$$\int_0^1 e^{2\pi i \omega x} \varphi(x) dx \cong \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta \varphi(x_\beta), \quad (1)$$

where C_β are coefficients, x_β are nodal points, $i^2 = -1$ and $\omega \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}$. The functions $\varphi(x)$ belong to the Hilbert space $W_2^{(m,0)}(0, 1)$, which is defined as

$$W_2^{(m,0)}(0, 1) = \{\varphi(x) : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \varphi^{(m-1)}(x) \text{ is absolutely continuous, } \varphi^{(m)}(x) \in L_2(0, 1)\}$$

is the Hilbert space of complex-valued functions, m is odd and in this space the inner product of two functions φ and ψ is defined by the equality

$$\langle \varphi, \psi \rangle = \int_0^1 (\varphi^{(m)}(x) + \varphi(x)) (\overline{\psi^{(m)}}(x) + \overline{\psi}(x)) dx, \quad (2)$$

where $\overline{\psi}$ is the conjugate function of the function ψ , and the norm of the function φ is accordingly determined by the formula

$$\|\varphi\| = \langle \varphi, \varphi \rangle^{1/2}.$$

and

$$\langle \varphi, \varphi \rangle^{1/2} = \int_0^1 (\varphi^{(m)}(x) + \varphi(x)) (\overline{\varphi^{(m)}}(x) + \overline{\varphi}(x)) dx < \infty.$$

Note that the coefficients C_β depend on ω, N and m , i.e. $C_\beta = C_\beta(\omega, N, m)$.

The difference between the integral and the quadrature sum in the considered quadrature formula (1)

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 e^{2\pi i \omega x} \varphi(x) dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta \varphi(x_\beta) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (\varepsilon_{[0,1]}(x) e^{2\pi i \omega x} - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta \delta(x - x_\beta)) \varphi(x) dx = \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \ell(x) \varphi(x) dx = (\ell, \varphi) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

is called the *error* of the quadrature formula.

For the derived expression (3), the following *error functional* corresponding to the conjugate space $W_2^{(m,0)*}(0,1)$ is obtained

$$\ell(x) = \varepsilon_{[0,1]}(x) e^{2\pi i \omega x} - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta \delta(x - x_\beta), \quad (4)$$

where $\varepsilon_{[0,1]}(x)$ is the characteristic function of the interval $[0, 1]$, and $\delta(x)$ is Dirac's delta-function.

According to the definition of the norm of a linear continuous functional, the following is known:

$$\|\ell\|_{W_2^{(m,0)*}} = \sup_{\|\varphi\| \neq 0} \frac{|(\ell, \varphi)|}{\|\varphi\|}.$$

From this equality, the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality follows

$$|(\ell, \varphi)| \leq \|\ell\|_{W_2^{(m,0)*}} \|\varphi\|_{W_2^{(m,0)}}.$$

To construct an optimal quadrature formula of the form (1) in the space $W_2^{(m,0)}(0,1)$, we need to find the coefficients C_β that satisfy the following equality

$$\|\mathring{\ell}\|_{W_2^{(m,0)*}} = \inf_{C_\beta} \|\ell\|_{W_2^{(m,0)*}(0,1)} \quad (5)$$

Thus, in this work we will sequentially solve the following problems.

Problem 1. Find the form of the norm of the error functional (4) of the quadrature formula (1) in the $W_2^{(m,0)}(0,1)$ space.

For this, we construct a quadrature formula at nodal points x_β where $x_\beta = h\beta$ ($h = \frac{1}{N}$, $N \in \mathbb{N}$) are equidistantly distributed points.

The coefficients C_β that minimize the norm of the error functional $\ell(x)$, that is are called *optimal coefficients* and are denoted by \mathring{C}_β . The quadrature formula constructed using these optimal coefficients is called an *optimal quadrature formula*. Therefore, to construct an optimal quadrature formula in the $W_2^{(m,0)}(0,1)$ space, it is necessary to solve the following problem.

Problem 2. Find the optimal coefficients \mathring{C}_β that achieve the value in (5).

Finding the extremal function and expressing the norm of the error functional

To solve problem 1, that is, to find the form of the norm of the error functional (4), we use the concept of an extremal function.

The function $\psi_\ell(x)$ is called an *extremal function* corresponding to the error functional $\ell(x)$ if the following equality holds [1,2,3]

$$(\ell, \psi_\ell) = \|\ell\|_{W_2^{(m,0)*}} \cdot \|\psi_\ell\|_{W_2^{(m,0)}}. \quad (6)$$

To obtain an explicit expression for the norm of the error functional (4) in the $W_2^{(m,0)*}(0,1)$ space we use the concept of the extremal function ψ_ℓ . Since $W_2^{(m,0)}(0,1)$ is a Hilbert space, the extremal function ψ_ℓ in this space can be found using Riesz's theorem. Then for the functional ℓ and for any $\varphi \in W_2^{(m,0)}(0,1)$ there exists a unique function $\psi_\ell \in W_2^{(m,0)}(0,1)$ for which the following equation holds

$$(\ell, \varphi) = \langle \psi_\ell, \varphi \rangle_{W_2^{(m,0)}} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\langle \psi_\ell, \varphi \rangle_{W_2^{(m,0)}} = \int_0^1 \left(\overline{\psi_\ell^{(m)}}(x) + \overline{\psi_\ell}(x) \right) (\varphi^{(m)}(x) + \varphi(x)) dx, \quad (8)$$

is an inner product defined in the $W_2^{(m,0)}(0,1)$ space. From (7), taking into account (8), for the extremal function ψ_ℓ we obtain the following boundary value problem

$$\psi_\ell^{(2m)}(x) - \psi_\ell(x) = (-1)^m \bar{\ell}(x) \quad (9)$$

with the boundary conditions

$$\left(\psi_\ell^{(m+s)}(x) + \psi_\ell^{(s)}(x) \right)_{x=0}^{x=1} = 0, \quad s = 0, 1, \dots, m-1, \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{\ell}$ is the adjoint functional to the functional ℓ .

Theorem. The solution of equation (9) with boundary conditions (10) is an extremal function ψ_ℓ of the error functional ℓ of quadrature formula (1) and has the form

$$\psi_\ell(x) = (-1)^m \bar{\ell}(x) * G_m(x) + d_0 e^{-x} + \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{m-1}{2}} e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \left[d_{1k} \cos \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) + d_{2k} \sin \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \right], \quad (11)$$

where

$$G_m(x) = \frac{\operatorname{sgn} x}{2m} \left[\sinh(x) + \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} e^{x \cos \frac{\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(x \sin \frac{\pi k}{m} + \frac{\pi k}{m} \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

is a solution to the equation

$$G_m^{(2m)} - G_m(x) = \delta(x), \quad (13)$$

d_0, d_{1k} and d_{2k} are any complex numbers, $*$ is convolution operation.

The theorem can be proved in the same way as Theorem 2.1 in [4].

Since the error functional (4) is defined on the space $W_2^{(m,0)}(0,1)$, it satisfies the following conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{\ell}, e^{-x}) &= 0, \left(\ell, e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \right) = 0, \\ \left(\ell, e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \right) &= 0, k = 1, \overline{\frac{m-1}{2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

From this it is clear that for quadrature formulas of the form (1) to exist, the condition $N + 1 \geq m$ must be satisfied. Equalities (14) mean that our quadrature formula is exact for the functions $e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right)$, $e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right)$ ($k = 1, \overline{\frac{m-1}{2}}$) and e^{-x} .

Now, using Theorem we obtain a representation of the squared norm of the error functional (4). Taking into account the definition of convolution and equality (4), we calculate the convolution $\bar{\ell}(x) * G_m(x)$, i.e.

$$\bar{\ell}(x) * G_m(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \bar{\ell}(y) G_m(x-y) dy = \int_0^1 e^{-2\pi i \omega y} G_m(x-y) dy - \sum_{\beta=0}^N \bar{C}_\beta G_m(x-h\beta),$$

where $\bar{\ell}$ and \bar{C}_β are conjugate to ℓ and C_β respectively.

Then, keeping in mind (7), (8) and the theorem, we obtain

$$\|\ell\|^2 = (\ell, \psi_\ell) = \langle \psi_\ell, \psi_\ell \rangle_{W_2^{(m,0)}} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \ell(x) \psi_\ell(x) dx = (-1)^m \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \ell(x) \cdot (\bar{\ell}(x) * G_m(x)) dx,$$

i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \|\ell\|^2 &= (-1)^m \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(e^{2\pi i \omega x} \varepsilon_{[0,1]}(x) - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta(x-h\beta) \right) \cdot \\ &\cdot \left(\int_0^1 e^{-2\pi i \omega y} G_m(x-y) dy - \sum_{\beta=0}^N \bar{C}_\beta G_m(x-h\beta) \right) dx. \end{aligned}$$

From here we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|\ell\|^2 &= (-1)^m \left[\sum_{\beta=0}^N \sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_\beta \bar{C}_\gamma G_m(h\beta - h\gamma) - \sum_{\beta=0}^N \int_0^1 (\bar{C}_\beta e^{2\pi i \omega x} + C_\beta e^{-2\pi i \omega x}) G_m(x-h\beta) dx \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_0^1 \int_0^1 e^{2\pi i \omega x} e^{-2\pi i \omega y} G_m(x-y) dx dy \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Let us now show that the right side of (15) is real. Indeed, let $C_\beta = C_\beta^R + iC_\beta^I$, where $i^2 = -1$, C_β^R and C_β^I are real. Using Euler's formula $e^{2\pi i \omega x} = \cos(2\pi \omega x) + i \sin(2\pi \omega x)$, we obtain the following equalities

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_\beta \bar{C}_\gamma G_m(h\beta - h\gamma) = \sum_{\beta=0}^N \sum_{\gamma=0}^N (C_\beta^R C_\gamma^R + C_\beta^I C_\gamma^I) G_m(h\beta - h\gamma),$$

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{C}_\beta e^{2\pi i \omega x} + C_\beta e^{-2\pi i \omega x} &= 2C_\beta^R \cos(2\pi \omega x) + 2C_\beta^I \sin(2\pi \omega x), \\ \int_0^1 \int_0^1 e^{2\pi i \omega x} e^{-2\pi i \omega y} G_m(x-y) dx dy &= \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \cos[2\pi \omega(x-y)] G_m(x-y) dx dy. \end{aligned}$$

Taking into account the last three equalities, from (15) for the norm of the error functional we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\ell\|^2 &= (-1)^m \left[\sum_{\beta=0}^N \sum_{\gamma=0}^N (C_\beta^R C_\gamma^R + C_\beta^I C_\gamma^I) G_m(h\beta - h\gamma) - 2 \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^R \int_0^1 \cos(2\pi \omega x) G_m(x - h\beta) dx \right. \\ &\quad \left. - 2 \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^I \int_0^1 \sin(2\pi \omega x) G_m(x - h\beta) dx + \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \cos[2\pi \omega(x-y)] G_m(x-y) dx dy \right] \quad (16) \end{aligned}$$

and from (14) we have the following equalities

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^R e^{-h\beta} = \int_0^1 e^{-x} \cos(2\pi \omega x) dx, \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^R e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos\left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m}\right) = \int_0^1 e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos\left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m}\right) \cos(2\pi \omega x) dx, \quad (18)$$

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^R e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin\left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m}\right) = \int_0^1 e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin\left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m}\right) \cos(2\pi \omega x) dx, \quad (19)$$

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^I e^{-h\beta} = \int_0^1 e^{-x} \sin(2\pi \omega x) dx, \quad (20)$$

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^I e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos\left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m}\right) = \int_0^1 e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos\left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m}\right) \sin(2\pi \omega x) dx, \quad (21)$$

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^I e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin\left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m}\right) = \int_0^1 e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin\left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m}\right) \sin(2\pi \omega x) dx. \quad (22)$$

Thus, problem 1 is solved. Next, we will solve problem 2.

System for optimal coefficients of quadrature formulas

The square of the norm (16) of the error functional (4) is a multivariable square function of the coefficients C_β^R and C_β^I . To find the minimum of the norm (16) of the error functional (4) with respect to the coefficients C_β^R and C_β^I under conditions (17)–(22), we apply Lagrange's method for finding a conditional extremum.

Let's consider the function

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi \left(C_0^R, \dots, C_N^R, C_0^I, \dots, C_N^I, d_0^R, d_0^I, d_{11}^R, \dots, d_{1\frac{m-1}{2}}^R, d_{11}^I, \dots, d_{1\frac{m-1}{2}}^I, d_{21}^R, \dots, d_{2\frac{m-1}{2}}^R, d_{21}^I, \dots, d_{2\frac{m-1}{2}}^I \right) = \|\ell\|^2 \\ -2(-1)^m d_0^R \left(\int_0^1 e^{-x} \cos(2\pi\omega x) dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^R e^{-h\beta} \right) - \\ -2(-1)^m d_0^I \left(\int_0^1 e^{-x} \sin(2\pi\omega x) dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^I e^{-h\beta} \right) \\ -2(-1)^m d_{1k}^R \left(\int_0^1 e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \cos(2\pi\omega x) dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^R e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \right) \\ -2(-1)^m d_{1k}^I \left(\int_0^1 e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \sin(2\pi\omega x) dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^I e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \right) \\ -2(-1)^m d_{2k}^R \left(\int_0^1 e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \cos(2\pi\omega x) dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^R e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \right) \\ -2(-1)^m d_{2k}^I \left(\int_0^1 e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \sin(2\pi\omega x) dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta^I e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

By equating the partial derivatives of the function Ψ with respect to C_β^R, C_β^I ($\beta = \overline{0, N}$), d_0^R, d_0^I ,

$d_{1k}^R, d_{1k}^I, d_{2k}^R$ and d_{2k}^I ($k = \overline{1, \frac{m-1}{2}}$) to zero, we obtain the following system of linear equations for

$\beta = 0, 1, \dots, N$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_\gamma^R G_m(h\beta - h\gamma) + d_0^R e^{-h\beta} + d_{1k}^R e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \\ + d_{2k}^R e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) = \int_0^1 \cos(2\pi\omega x) G_m(x - h\beta) dx, \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

$$\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_\gamma^R e^{-h\gamma} = \int_0^1 e^{-x} \cos(2\pi\omega x) dx, \quad (24)$$

$$\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_\gamma^R e^{-h\gamma \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(h\gamma \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) = \int_0^1 e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \cos(2\pi\omega x) dx, \quad (25)$$

$$\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_\gamma^R e^{-h\gamma \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(h\gamma \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) = \int_0^1 e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \cos(2\pi\omega x) dx, \quad (26)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\gamma}^I G_m(h\beta - h\gamma) + d_0^I e^{-h\beta} + d_{1k}^I e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \\ & + d_{2k}^I e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) = \int_0^1 \sin(2\pi\omega x) G_m(x - h\beta) dx, \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

$$\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\gamma}^I e^{-h\gamma} = \int_0^1 e^{-x} \sin(2\pi\omega x) dx, \quad (28)$$

$$\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\gamma}^I e^{-h\gamma \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(h\gamma \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) = \int_0^1 e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \sin(2\pi\omega x) dx, \quad (29)$$

$$\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\gamma}^I e^{-h\gamma \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(h\gamma \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) = \int_0^1 e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \sin(2\pi\omega x) dx. \quad (30)$$

Now, multiplying both sides of equalities (27) - (30) by i and adding to both sides (23) - (26) respectively, using the notations $C_{\beta} = C_{\beta}^R + C_{\beta}^I$, $d_0 = d_0^R + id_0^I$, $d_{1k} = d_{1k}^R + id_{1k}^I$ and $d_{2k} = d_{2k}^R + id_{2k}^I$ ($k = \overline{1, \frac{m-1}{2}}$) for the coefficients of optimal quadrature formulas of the form (1), we obtain the following system $N + m + 1$ of linear equations and $\beta = 0, 1, \dots, N$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\gamma} G_m(h\beta - h\gamma) + d_0 e^{-h\beta} + d_{1k} e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) \\ & + d_{2k} e^{-h\beta \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(h\beta \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) = f_m(h\beta), \quad \beta = 0, 1, \dots, N, \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

$$\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\gamma} e^{-h\gamma} = \int_0^1 e^{2\pi i \omega x} e^{-x} dx, \quad (32)$$

$$\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\gamma} e^{-h\gamma \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(h\gamma \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) = \int_0^1 e^{2\pi i \omega x} e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \cos \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) dx, \quad (33)$$

$$\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\gamma} e^{-h\gamma \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(h\gamma \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) = \int_0^1 e^{2\pi i \omega x} e^{-x \cos \frac{2\pi k}{m}} \sin \left(x \sin \frac{2\pi k}{m} \right) dx, \quad (34)$$

where $G_m(x)$ is defined by equality (13),

$$f_m(h\beta) = \int_0^1 e^{2\pi i \omega x} G_m(x - h\beta) dx. \quad (35)$$

It should be noted that system (31) - (34) has a unique solution and this solution yields the minimum of the squared norm (16) of the error functional (4) under conditions (32) - (34). The uniqueness of the solution to this system is obtained in [5].

From (16) and from the work [5] it follows that the square of the norm of the error functional ℓ , which is a quadratic function of the coefficients C_β , has a unique minimum at some specific value $C_\beta = \mathring{C}_\beta$. The quadrature formula and the coefficients \mathring{C}_β ($\beta = 0, 1, \dots, N$), corresponding to this minimum are called the optimal quadrature formula and \mathring{C}_β are called the optimal coefficients.

References:

1. Sobolev S.L. Introduction to the Theory of Cubature Formulas. *M.: Nauka*. 808 p. 1974.
2. Sobolev S.L., Vaskevich V.L. The theory of cubature formulas. *Kluwer Academic Publishers Group*. - *Dordrecht*. 484 p. 1997.
3. Shadimetov Kh.M. Optimal lattice quadrature and cubature formulas in Sobolev spaces. *Tashkent, Fan va texnologiya*. 224 p. 2019.
4. Boltaev A.K., Hayotov A.R., Shadimetov Kh.M.; Construction of optimal quadrature formulas exact for exponential-trigonometric functions by Sobolev's method. *Acta Mathematica Sinica, English series*, 37(7), pp. 1066-1088, (2021).
5. Boltaev A.K. Existence and uniqueness of the solution for a linear system of optimal coefficients. *Uzbek Mathematical Journal*, 67(2), pp. 31-38, 2023.

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